

The Motivation Behind Consistent Self-Access Center Attendees: A Student Perspective

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Abstract: *Since the opening of the self-access center (SAC) at Kagawa University, we have observed that a small number of students become regular SAC attendees but the majority of students who attend the center only do so sporadically. By adopting a mixed-method approach, this study sought to discover how these long-term attendees first heard about the SAC, what motivated them to attend frequently, what their experiences in the center were, and finally how feedback from these students might be used to encourage more students to become regular SAC attendees. Initial indications are that a recommendation from friends played a crucial role in raising their awareness of the SAC, and was an important factor in motivating their first attendance. Although these students acknowledged that academic factors affected their long-term attendance, it was the friendships established within the SAC, including those with international students, that served as the primary motivation for their continued attendance.*

Keywords: self-access, motivation, learner autonomy

Introduction

Self-access centers (SAC), sometimes called self-access language learning centers, are educational facilities designed for language learning that are mostly self-directed. They promote the development of autonomous language learners and thus encourage students to study what they believe is necessary for them from the resources available (Gardner & Miller, 2011). The development of SACs stems from the theory that foreign and second language learners learn better if they are independent learners who have autonomy over what and how they learn. Educators have argued for a more reflective and learner-centered approach to language teaching with learners taking more responsibility for their own learning (Klassen, et al., 1998; Morrison, 2008). What is

more, many researchers believe there should be a greater focus on the development of effective learning strategies and the development of the independent learner (e.g. Dörnyei, 2001).

The extent to which learners engage in autonomous or independent learning varies depending on the pedagogical philosophies and goals of each individual SAC. In the most extreme form of self-directed learning, the teacher's role is to only support and give feedback while it is the learners themselves who set their own curriculum and goals and evaluate their progress. In countries such as Japan where students are more used to teacher-led activities, this most extreme approach to self-directed learning can be problematic as learners need extensive guidance and support so as to not become overwhelmed or lost when using a SAC (Thompson & Atkinson, 2010). This need for guidance can become time-consuming for staff and in a sense, defeats the purpose of the SAC. Even in countries that traditionally adopt a more independent approach to teaching and learning, studies have shown that learners do not seem to want too much freedom in defining and assessing their own learning (Lai, 1999). Because of these issues, many SACs adopt a semi-guided learning system where the SAC holds a mixture of classes and events, while at the same time encouraging students to become more independent learners by allowing them to choose a diverse mixture of self-directed or teachers-dependent classes, activities, and events. Usually, SACs adopting this approach have teachers and other staff readily available to give academic and psychological support. Student responses to this style of SAC management have often been positive, or very positive (Rodden, 2007).

The self-access center at Kagawa University, which opened in 2014, has adopted a semi-guided learning system with four main objectives: bridging the gap between guided/classroom-taught language learning and independent learning, enabling the learner to improve both linguistic proficiency and independent learning skills, providing a space to help exchange and foreign students integrate into the university community, and providing language learning support for all students. Despite having a wide range of classes and activities, teachers and staff at the SAC have found that while a small number of students become regular attendees, often attending the SAC several times a week and in some cases every day, the majority of students attend only sporadically if at all. Unfortunately, this is not a problem unique to Kagawa University, and student motivation to attend a SAC has become an important area of research over the past 10 to 15 years. Lave and Wenger (1991) identified different levels of participation in their research into legitimate peripheral participation in classroom research (Figure 1) and their work has frequently been applied to research in SAC attendance and participation patterns (e.g. Wenger et al., 2002). This "core group" and "active group" of learners in Lave and Wenger's model are most comparable with our frequent attendees in terms of participation patterns. Moreover, these frequent attendees have created a community of practice which support each other within the framework of the SAC. Similar situations have been found at other SAC such as in Tassinari (2017).

Figure 1. Levels of participation (Lave & Wenger, 1991)

SACs present opportunities for international exchange, language exchange, self-study, and social interaction but this latter aspect seems to be the main driving force behind students deciding to continuously attend. As noted by Hughes et al., (2012) the majority of students who begin attending SACs do so for academic purposes but continue to attend for social reasons. In the same paper, Hughes et al. outline a list of keywords taken from student comments pertaining to their continued attendance. These keywords consist of: “with, people, students, friends, exchange, them, talk, others, fun, feel, atmosphere.”

However, universities face some amount of difficulty concerning the promotion of attendance at SACs. Posters, websites, and mentions by lecturers may attract a small number of students, but by and large, the majority of students attend due to direct influence from peers and seniors. Mayeda et al., (2008) discuss a situation at Shoin Women’s University wherein three friends of a regular SAC attendee were inspired to attend themselves after witnessing their classmate’s academic achievements which were attributed to her time spent at the SAC. This interest spread to a further eight students, who all began attending.

As this previous account illustrates, the academic benefits reaped by the first student had a major knock-on effect on other students. However, it may not just be academic achievements alone that spurred this interest. Gillies (2010) posits that a desired future self-image can also be a major factor in choosing to join a SAC. Having witnessed a peer display attributes synonymous with success, the aforementioned students may have been inspired to envision an internal roadmap towards a better future self-image that incorporates a SAC.

Research Questions and Methodology

To help us understand why some students at this university frequently and continuously attend the SAC for an extended period of time and to discover if we could replicate similar results to the studies mentioned above, we analyzed the data collected from daily attendance records, class

records, and special events attendance records. From this, we (the research team, teachers, and staff at the SAC) identified students over the three-year period that we considered to be “frequent attendees”. We defined “frequent attendees” as those who attend the SAC at least twice a week for a minimum of 12 weeks of a 15-week semester. Once we had identified these students we sought to answer three questions:

- 1 How did these students first hear about the SAC?
- 2 Why did they first, and then, continue to attend?
- 3 Could feedback from these students help us to create a more student-friendly space that would encourage more students to attend regularly?

We adopted a mixed-methods approach to our research. Firstly, a three-part mostly multi-choice questionnaire was administered at the end of the autumn semesters of 2019, 2020, and 2021 (Appendix 1). All participants in 2020, and those at a satellite campus in 2019 and 2021, were sent and returned the questionnaire by email. Students at the main campus (2019, 2021) were sent the questionnaire by email but were asked to complete the questionnaire and when finished, return it to the SAC in person (mostly to ask them if they would be willing and available to participate in an interview). In total, 82 students were identified as frequent attendees and questionnaires were sent to 30 of them; 28 completed the questionnaire (Table 1). We only sent the questionnaire to 30 students as we had discovered in the past that students in their fourth year who were graduating, or those who had gone abroad (either on holiday or part of an exchange programme), were unlikely to check their university email and respond to the questionnaire. Moreover, since we thought it may be necessary to conduct interviews with at least some students, we wanted to collect data from students who were readily available.

The data from the questionnaire was then tabulated to facilitate comparison and analysis. Following the administration of the questionnaires, we conducted interviews with 15 students. These interviews were recorded, transcribed, and analyzed. Informed consent was received from all participants.

Table 1. Study Setting – number of SAC attendees during the academic years 2019–2022

	2019–2020	2020–2021*	2021–2022 **
Total #number of Attendees	3240	1330	1087
Number of regular attendees (number of students who completed and returned the questionnaire)	40 (15)	17 (7)	25 (8)

* Online/remote teaching and events only; **online/hybrid, restricted opening hours

The effect of the COVID-19 pandemic can be seen in the above figures. For the academic year 2020–2021, the SAC conducted classes and events online but no events were held in the actual SAC facility. When the SAC reopened to students in July 2021, we had restricted hours and limited the number of students (and staff/teachers) that could be in the SAC at the same time. As a result, many classes and events continued to be offered either totally online or in a hybrid fashion. This had a detrimental effect on student attendance at the SAC, and it is only now (2022–2023) that figures are closer to pre-pandemic levels (2800 attendees in the academic year 2022–2023).

Results and Discussion

Although this study was limited by the COVID-19 pandemic and the closure and/or reduced opening hours of the SAC, we were able to discover some interesting factors that encouraged initial and continued attendance.

Part 1 of the questionnaire focused on gathering background information such as the year of first attendance, gender, and perceived English-speaking ability. A lot of this information was needed by the SAC for administrative purposes but in some cases, proved interesting for research purposes too.

Figure 2. Breakdown of Students by University Year when they first attended the SAC (n=28)

There was an almost even split between male and female students, and the majority of frequent attendees were first or second years with slightly more students in their second year than first year (Figure 2). Fewer students continued to attend the SAC when in their third and fourth year, mostly due to increased course workload and job hunting. Some students mentioned, compared with their first/second year at university, increased part-time working hours as another reason for this. Students considered their spoken English abilities to be low to intermediate (Figure 3). However, most of these students could communicate quite well, and without any access to formal test results that assess speaking ability (e.g. Eiken, IELTS, TOEIC S & W), we would probably describe most of them as intermediate to upper-intermediate learners.

Figure 3. Students’ Self-Reported Spoken English Level (n=28)

In this section too, we asked students whether they considered themselves to be “shy” “outgoing” or a “neither/mixture of both”. Most students answered that they were either “shy” or a “mixture of shy and outgoing”. From anecdotal evidence, many students who do not attend the SAC believe that students in attendance are very outgoing, fluent English speakers mirroring the opinions of many teachers.

Part 2 of the questionnaire focused on students’ first experience attending the SAC and what motivated them to continue attending. Questions were multi-choice and students could usually select more than one answer. When asked in the questionnaire how they first heard about the SAC, nearly all the students indicated that usually senior students, friends, and teachers mentioned or recommended it (Figure 4). Students were allowed to choose more than one answer as some students could not remember clearly if they had heard about it from a friend, another student, or from a class teacher. What is clear, however, is that traditional forms of advertising such as posters or emails did not suffice to attract students’ attention. In fact, only three students mentioned seeing a poster or flyer for the SAC despite them being displayed liberally throughout the campus. Furthermore, only two students could remember receiving information about the SAC and its events at the official university orientation and guidance sessions held during their first week.

Figure 4. How students first heard about the SAC (n=28)

We next asked students why they first attended the SAC (Figure 5) and how they would describe this experience (positive or negative). Students were allowed to choose more than one reason for their initial attendance. Improving their language ability (an academic factor) and making friends with other Japanese students (a social factor), as well as interacting with international students (a social factor) were important motivators for first attendance. We were interested in any reasons that were outside our expectations so included the category “other” as one of the possible responses. We received a large variety of responses to this including “eat lunch”, “read a book”, “watch TV” “sleep” and “relax”. These responses illustrate the wide spectrum of how students view the SAC facilities.

Figure 5. Reasons for first attendance

Most students found their initial visit a bit intimidating, with eight finding it negative and 11 finding it both a positive and negative experience confirming what other researchers (e.g. Hughes, 2012) reported. This negative experience during students’ first visit to the SAC was one of the areas that initiated our desire to conduct post-survey interviews since most students did not expand on why they had found their initial experience negative or mixed. In particular, we wanted to discover if there was anything we could do to rectify this situation. When asked to choose a primary reason for their continued attendance, the majority of students indicated either social (15) or academic (8) responses as their primary reason for continuing.

Part 3 of the questionnaire surveyed the type of classes and events students attended, how often they attended these, and how they would rate the quality of these events. Students rated classes/events highly, attended a wide range of these classes/events, and “dropped by” the SAC at least 3.3 days/week on average. In this section, we also asked students to write any comments or suggestions they had about their experiences in the SAC, but unfortunately, the majority of students wrote very little or nothing at all.

Although useful data was obtained through the questionnaire, the multi-choice nature of the questions did not give students the opportunity to freely express their opinions regarding their experiences at the SAC. Moreover, since students could choose more than one response we wanted to clarify some points, in particular those regarding their primary reasons for their first and continued attendance, and their negative first experiences. We therefore decided to conduct interviews and to date, one of the authors (McCrohan) has conducted 15 follow-up interviews (Table 2).

Table 2. Post-questionnaire interview (student profiles) N=15

	1st year	2nd year	3rd year +
Economics	1	2	
Education		1	1
Law	2	2	
Medicine/Nursing	2		
Technology	2	1	1

These interviews were done online (using Zoom) and were later transcribed, coded into broad areas such as “responsibility”, “improving spoken English”, and analysed to determine what common themes emerged. Due to previous research in this area we expected to discover certain themes, and as a result we adapted a deductive approach to coding. Each interview was read carefully, and all the phrases and sentences that matched specific codes were highlighted. We then collated all the data into groups identified by specific codes. These codes allowed us to gain a condensed overview of the main points and common meanings that recurred throughout the data. Finally, we combined several codes into a single themes.

Overall four themes emerged from the interviews:

- a. the importance of social connections fostered by SAC attendance
- b. “ownership” of events or “responsibility” for the success of the SAC
- c. academic success (improved language abilities)
- d. “other” – in particular a space to relax and feel at ease

Wanting to see if students would give similar answers to those they gave in the survey, the interviews opened by asking students how they first heard about the SAC and what their purpose was the first time they attended. The majority of students, as in the questionnaire, mentioned a recommendation from a friend, another student, or teacher as the means through which they heard about the SAC. When asked about why they attended, the largest category was for academic reasons (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Reasons for 1st attendance (from interviews) (n=15)

Six students said they initially went for primarily academic reasons such as improving their spoken English abilities or wanting to study abroad “I joined a speaking class in the Global Café. This is because I hope to be able speak English well, and I want to go to Australia or New Zealand for

study abroad" (law major, second year); two technology first-year students mentioned that their teacher for their general education classes offered bonus points for SAC attendance and that also influenced them to attend as they would get a higher grade for the class. When students mentioned a teacher it was often because either, the teacher gave "bonus points" (an academic reason) for attendance, or the student had asked for help in improving their speaking and/or listening skills. For example, an education major in her third year mentioned that his English Composition teacher recommended he attend the Global Café to "level up" his English, in particular his speaking and listening.

Only three mentioned social reasons. Two students mentioned their "sempai" or senior students, with one saying, "My sempai recommended the Global Café for me. She said it was the good place to meet international students and have fun events like Christmas and Halloween party." (economics major, second year). The final student who gave a social reason said, "My friend wanted to go to the Global Café because she wants..wanted to meet with foreign students. She is shy... and...but she and I went to there together." These responses were typical of what many students had said regarding social activities in the SAC even when not talking about their first attendance.

However, when asked why they continued, six of the attendees stated that they continued to attend primarily for social reasons, while five reported academic reasons as their primary source of motivation (Figure 7). Academic reasons included getting bonus points from some teachers for SAC attendance, however, when we removed students who mentioned these bonus points as their principal motivation for attendance, only two students said that their attendance was for primarily academic reasons. Both of these students stated that improving their English results on the TOEIC was important to them. One student was in his third year, the other in his second, and had already taken the TOEIC in their first year, but intended to take the TOEIC again so they could include their TOEIC results on job applications. Moreover, the third-year student mentioned that English skills would be important for him when he applied to, and hopefully continued on to graduate school. The second-year student wanted to get good results in his general education English classes, in particular, his presentation and writing classes. Despite these extrinsic goals driving the attendance of these two students, we can see that social reasons are the dominant motivation for continued attendance.

Figure 7. Reasons for continued attendance (from interviews) (n=15)

During the interviews, it appeared that the academic reasons for their continued attendance

declined in importance while the social elements increased. Students were able to talk extensively about the social side of the SAC and while they saw the importance of the SAC to their studies, most seemed to place an emphasis on the social bonds they had created in the SAC confirming findings by Zaragoza (2011) and Hughes (2012). This was reflected in changes in their use of vocabulary with increased usage of words and phrases associated with the social side of the SAC in the interviews, compared with the vocabulary used when discussing the reasons for their initial attendance. In particular, students frequently mentioned “making friends”, “meeting friends/ spending time with friends” “meeting new people”, “meeting/talking with international students”, “playing/hanging out”, and “relaxing” when giving reasons for their continued attendance. In contrast, when talking about their initial reason for attending, students frequently used what we classified as academic reasons such as “improving/developing my English speaking skills”, “learning new vocabulary”, and “studying abroad”. Even when talking about academic activities (classes/self-study) in the SAC students often brought up the social element of their experience. For example, a second-year education major student said that while he started attending the “movie class” in the SAC, he continued not only out of interest in this, but also because he had now made new friends who a similar interests to him.

It appeared from the interviews that many students (10) first attended the Global Café for “English/International Lunch.” As the name infers, this was held at lunchtime, students could bring their own lunch, talk with other students in English, or listen to a presentation given by an international student or a Japanese student who had returned from an exchange programme. These lunchtime events are usually very well attended and may partially explain students’ negative first experience. A third-year law major explained that because of how busy the SAC was the first time he attended, he had difficulty finding a place to sit, and had problems joining a conversation that was already in progress.

This student had indicated on the questionnaire that their first experience was both “negative and positive” so we asked what happened next. He said that thanks to the attentive staff, he was quickly engaged conversation with other students. He also mentioned that the following week, he arrived a little earlier so did not have a problem finding a place to sit. Another student who had only indicated a “negative” first experience explained that the SAC was quite empty when she first attended and as a result, she was nervous. However, when asked why she returned following such a negative experience she said that the next time she attended with a friend, and that they participated in a “Halloween decoration” activity which helped her feel relaxed and comfortable.

The experience of these students would suggest that the atmosphere (too crowded or too empty) can have a significant impact on the students first experience and is something that must be taken into consideration by the staff. In particular, the staff (or student volunteers) need to be quick to integrate students into an ongoing activity, and by doing this, they can reduce the anxiety students may feel. Conversely, they too need to find a way to make students feel comfortable when the SAC is mostly empty, for example, by having areas of the SAC that are not so open, or having a ready-made range of activities students can try by themselves or in pairs. Something as simple as just talking with these students, making them feel welcome, may be enough to put them at ease.

Of special interest were words and phrases associated with “responsibility” and “helping” in motivating students to continue to attend. Figure 8 shows in percentages (to more easily facilitate comparisons between different grades) the areas for which students felt they had a responsibility. Over time, these students who frequently attended the SAC developed a sense of responsibility

to help run the SAC effectively and to assist other students (both Japanese and international/exchange students). Students indicated they were involved in many areas in the SAC from helping run events, to decorating, to helping with classes or encouraging others to attend. In particular, students mentioned assisting with “welcome events” held in April, the start of the academic year.

Figure 8. Student Areas of Responsibility (in %) (n=28)

A master’s student in technology who started attending a wide variety of both SAC classes and events in her first year as an undergraduate explained that while she at first felt reluctant to help organize events, she realized that the SAC had had a big impact on her university life and she therefore felt a responsibility to help promote it to other students, and to help with the management of events (and even classes) too. Helping foreign students was common for second-to-fourth-year students. From the interviews, several students mentioned helping foreign students with their daily life in Japan such as going shopping, joining a gym, or even going to a doctor or dentist.

In addition, many students believed they also had a responsibility to help other Japanese students. For those in the upper grades, this often included academic support, from helping/teaching content to choosing classes. Assisting others with social (as apposed to academic) issues was common for students in all grades. As a 1st year medical student stated, “My friend is lonely because she is far away from her family in Aichi. She is feeling better these days because of her friends in the Global Café.”

A theme that we found especially interesting, and even heartwarming was how students described their feelings towards the SAC. All students interviewed mentioned the sense of “belonging” with regard to the SAC. Some called it their “home” and two even described the other members (and staff) as their “university family”. The feeling of being included was given a lot of importance by students in the interviews. Quotations include, “The Global Cafe is my home. I hang out there and feel comfortable in there.” And, “I am not good at social. My family says I am KY* but in Global Café I am easy.” (*KY = “someone who cannot read the mood” of a social group). These quotations and many other similar ones highlight the social importance of the SAC, especially for students who are away from home for the first time, and also for those who may be neurodivergent in some way, and who normally have problems interacting with others socially.

Finally, two of the students interviewed had participated in TOEIC Speaking and Writing classes that utilized peer tutors. Since the inception of the SAC, we have run classes to help students prepare for the TOEIC S & W test. Usually these classes are conducted by a faculty member from the university General Education section team-teaching with the SAC coordinator. Due to scheduling

conflicts in the year 2019, the SAC coordinator was unavailable for some of these classes, and as a result, we decided to ask students who had taken the test previously to be “student teachers” (peer tutors). The use of peer tutors in these TOEIC S & W preparation classes has proven to be successful at this university. Students found peer tutors to be linguistic role models and increased the likelihood of students asking questions since they were less intimidated by peer tutors than university faculty (McCrohan & Caldwell, 2021). Both of these students mentioned how much they appreciated these classes and how their peer tutors inspired them to be better language learners and speakers.

There are a number of issues with this study. Most importantly, as was mentioned in a report of the JASAL forum at JALT 2022 (McCrohan et al. 2023), this study features a small number of participants at one institution, there are several limitations that must be considered, primarily the lack of adequate data and statistics due to the small number of participants. We had initially hoped to continue researching this area with a similar number of students in each academic year, but due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting changes to the academic calendar and the closure of the SAC, followed by a limited number of participants and opening hours, this was impossible. Comparing the findings of this study with those compiled at other SACs, we have found certain similarities but also some additional findings. More longitudinal and comparative research with other institutions is needed to determine what other factors may be of influence in determining students’ continued SAC attendance.

The effect of the COVID-19 pandemic must also be considered when looking at the results of this study. Since we were using emergency remote teaching for the 2020 academic year, we did not have first-year students “dropping by” the SAC as was common in other years. As a result, our attendance for this year, and for at least the following academic year, may not reflect normal attendance patterns. We believe that this is partly the reason for the reduced number of frequent attendees in the 2021 academic year. However, it is of note that despite the limitations imposed by the need for social distancing, we still had a core group of attendees who continued to frequently attend the online classes and events, and came in-person to the SAC when the pandemic restrictions were eased.

Practical Applications

A number of practical factors came to light during the course of this study. First and foremost, what cannot be ignored in this discussion is the environment itself. (Edlin, 2016) notes that universities tend to not give appropriate consideration to the learning environment design of their SACs. Students are used to the controlled learning environments afforded by their regular classrooms. SACs, on the other hand, tend to offer a mix of controlled and uncontrolled situations. There may be lectures, discussions, self-study, or any number of other activities taking place at an SAC at any time. For a new student, this experience can be disorientating and have a negative impact. Furthermore, the size, layout, furniture, and decoration of the space can range from enticing to intimidating (Oblinger, 2006) and this is something mentioned by some of our participants in the interviews. They found the open-plan design of the SAC, with large windows allowing everyone to see in (a fish-bowl atmosphere), a bit offputting, especially at first. All of this taken into consideration, it can be stated that careful thought needs to be given to the environmental design of the SAC should continued student attendance be a goal of the institution.

The timing of a student's initial participation is also of importance. From the negative experiences mentioned by students, it would suggest that the atmosphere (too crowded or too empty) can have a significant impact on their first experience. To overcome this issue, the role of either SAC staff or already established student attendees in quickly incorporating new arrivals into an activity and helping them feel at ease is paramount to retention.

Fostering a sense of community through shared ownership and responsibilities within the SAC is likely to encourage frequent attendance. SACs should prioritize this structure to maximize growth. This can be achieved by, for example, inviting students to participate in teaching or assisting with classes, organizing and managing events, and contributing to the decoration of the SAC. This aligns with previous research findings emphasizing the significance of community in student engagement with a SAC (Murray & Fujishima, 2013; Oblinger, 2006), and a sense of responsibility for the success of the SAC. It is clear that, given a sense of ownership over their environment, students choose to invest their time and passion into its health and development. Furthermore, fostering bonds between international students and Japanese students from various faculties and academic levels presents a vital path towards creating a vibrant, rewarding community.

Finally, though this research, we can assert that traditional advertising did not seem to have made a lasting impression, at least with creating awareness of the SAC. We found that it is best for the staff and teachers at the SAC to focus on encouraging students already in attendance to reach out to their peers in order to grow the overall number of participants. Students have much greater sway over their peers than traditional advertising, information given at new student orientation, and even suggestions from teachers outside of the SAC.

Conclusion

The roles of staff and students, the physical arrangement and design of the space available, and the pedagogical goals and objectives of the centre are just a few of the factors to consider when establishing a SAC. Numerous studies have been conducted on these topics, and there is a growing body of research into autonomous learner development in a SAC setting, student use of the materials and resources available, and variables that may influence a student's initial and sustained participation in a SAC. While recognizing the significance of academic factors, this study along with work done by others (e.g. Hughes, 2012; Murray & Fujishima, 2013), found that the primary motivation for students' sustained involvement in a SAC stemmed from the friendships and communities established within it.

Moreover, in line with other researchers, we found that traditional advertising did not entice students to attend the SAC, but word-of-mouth, especially from their peers played a major role. With participation numbers seen as a crucial matter for most SACs, this presents a conundrum for the SAC teachers and staff: How can we effectively balance the provision of high-quality academic pursuits if possible involving students in leadership roles, while at the same time fostering robust social networks? Navigating this challenge requires a nuanced approach. The SAC should not be relegated to a mere social meeting place, nor should it be overly structured around academic activities. The former would reduce it to a social club, while the latter could alienate students and strip them of agency. The assignment of formal roles to students in the management and running of the SAC, in addition to the voluntary mentoring roles students have adopted, should result in maintaining student autonomy and agency. Thus, teachers, staff and students alike must strive to

find a middle ground - a space where student agency and meaningful social interactions harmonize with a setting rich in academic possibilities.

Therefore, more work must be done to assist current students (both Japanese and international) in making the most of their time at the SAC, and to entice more less linguistically proficient students to participate and continue to participate in the SAC. With this in mind, we have two research areas for future studies. First, we would like to focus on the more peripheral users of our SAC. In particular, we feel there is a need to investigate why some students only occasionally attend a SAC, and why the attendance of some who initially attend frequently, can taper off. Since these students have/had the motivation to attend the SAC at least occasionally or attend frequently and then drop out, it would suggest that the SAC is failing to meet the needs of these students. Another area we are interested in, is the role the SAC has in the experience of foreign and/or exchange students who are attending university in Japan. As one of the aims of our SAC is to help with the integration of these learners into the student body, we would be interested in learning how they perceive the environment of the SAC, and how it could be utilized to improve their experience of university life in Japan.

Finding an equilibrium between students' academic and social needs, while at the same time integrating all students no matter what their background or linguistic levels, holds the key to transforming the SAC into a welcoming, socially vibrant, and academically stimulating environment. Such a balance could lead to an upswing in regular attendees, fostering a positive and inclusive atmosphere within the SAC.

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Appendix A: Global Café Attendance Questionnaire

Part 1: Background

Name: _____ Student Number: _____

Current Year: 1 2 3 4 Grad Int. Faculty: _____

1. When did you start learning English? Please circle.

Kindergarten	Elementary school 1–3
Elementary school 4–6	JHS
Speak English at home	Other _____

2. As a child did you attend an language school (英会話) Y/N?

If “yes” for how many years? _____

get help with homework/assignment (language class)	
get help with homework/assignment (non-language class)	
Other (please explain)	

10. Why did you continue to attend the GC? Check all that apply.

meet friends	
make new friends	
meet international students	
study for language classes	
study for non-language classes	
get help with homework/assignment (language classes)	
get help with homework/assignment (non-language class)	
learn another foreign language (not taught in regular university language classes)	
learn about other countries and/or cultures	
take a GC class (not study abroad)	
take a GC study abroad course	
participate in GC events	
teacher recommended you attend	
receive bonus points/extra credit for regular university class	
travel/vacation	
future job	
Other (please explain)	

11. Did you attend classes this semester? Yes No
 If "yes" what classes did you attend?

12. How would you rate these classes?
 1 = poor 2 = average 3 = good 4 = very good 5 = excellent

1 2 3 4 5

13. Did you attend any events this semester? Yes No
 If "yes", how many? _____

14. If yes, how would you rate these classes?
 1 = poor 2 = average 3 = good 4 = very good 5 = excellent

1 2 3 4 5

15. How would you rate your overall experience at the GC

1 = poor 2 = average 3 = good 4 = very good 5 = excellent

1 2 3 4 5

16. Would you recommend the GC to other students? Yes No Maybe

Part 3. We would like to hear your opinion about your GC experience

You can write in English or Japanese.

17. What do you like and/or dislike about the GC?

18. Is there anything you would like to change about the GC?

19. Is there anything else you would like to say?

Thank you for your time.